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Power Line Communication as a Sensor: Medium Voltage Cable Diagnostics

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ABSTRACT

This article explores the secondary use of power line communication (PLC) technology, specifically broadband power line (BPL), as a diagnostic tool for medium voltage (MV) cable lines. Through experimental measurements, it was confirmed that selected communication parameters of BPL modems exhibit measurable deviations in the presence of partial discharge (PD) activity. Specifically, the parameters considered are throughput, signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), link capacity, bit load estimate (BLE), transmission amplitude map, Tonemap (modulation scheme), and Tonemask. In particular, BPL throughput decreased by approximately 10 Mbps for 100 pC PD and by around 50% for 1,000 pC PD. Since partial discharges are an early indicator of insulation system degradation, their detection supports predictive maintenance and contributes to improving the operational reliability of distribution networks. The results demonstrate that PLC/BPL technology—originally designed for communication and automation of distribution transformer stations (DTS)—can also serve as a cost-effective and readily deployable sensor system for real-time monitoring of cable health, without the need for dedicated diagnostic equipment. Experiments employing both inductive and capacitive couplers confirm the effectiveness of this secondary application in detecting insulation-related anomalies.

1 | Introduction

In today's era of rapid technological transformation, the energy industry plays a key role in meeting society's ever-increasing needs. With the advancing development of modern technologies, new solutions for more efficient and reliable control of power networks appear on the front stage, and power line communication (PLC) technology is one of the possible communication technologies that have a place in this area [1, 2].

The global demand for energy sources is increasing. Above all, there is a growing interest in producing energy from renewable sources in the home, which brings the need for more efficient management and monitoring of high-voltage networks. With its ability to transmit data over power lines, the PLC provides a convenient approach that eliminates the need for extensive new

infrastructure construction. As this technology integrates into existing power networks, the door opens to new possibilities for almost real-time network monitoring, diagnosis, and control [3, 4].

Looking at medium-voltage PLC applications, the question arises as to how this technology responds to the challenges of modern power systems. We examine how PLC can improve the reliability of electricity transmission, minimize losses, and contribute to more efficient grids. This is crucial in light of the increasing energy sustainability and security demands.

The primary purpose of PLC technology is as one of the possible communication techniques used in distribution networks for the purpose of substation automation and integration into the supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA) system. Suitable use

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can be seen, for example, in substations in urban areas, where substations are often in basements, where there is no 4G LTE/5G network coverage, and the installation of external antennas can be problematic. The secondary use of PLC can be seen in already installed networks and use the technology for on-line detection of the current state of cable lines. The measured parameters of PLC modems can even detect discharge activity on medium voltage (MV) cables. However, conventional on-line partial discharge monitoring systems are typically expensive, require dedicated sensors, and are therefore deployed only at selected critical locations. In contrast, PLC infrastructure is often already present in distribution networks for communication purposes. Leveraging existing PLC modems for secondary diagnostic functionality can thus provide a cost-effective and scalable approach to continuous cable condition monitoring without additional sensing hardware.

MV cables are a key component of urban cable distribution networks and the operation of the entire electricity system, including the monitored indicators system average interruption duration index (SAIDI) and system average interruption frequency index (SAIFI), depends on their operational reliability [5].

$$\text{SAIDI}_h = \frac{\sum_j t_{sjh}}{N_{sh}} \quad [\text{minutes/year/customer}] \quad (1)$$

$$\text{SAIFI}_h = \frac{\sum_j n_{jh}}{N_{sh}} \quad [\text{interruption/year/customer}] \quad (2)$$

where:

- n_{jh} —the total number of customers supplied from voltage level h affected by the supply interruption caused by event j occurring on level h or higher levels,
- N_{sh} —the total number of customers directly supplied from voltage level h ,
- t_{sjh} —the sum of all outage durations of electricity supply due to event j for customers directly supplied from voltage level h .

From the perspective of distribution system operators, failures of medium-voltage cable networks represent a significant operational and economic challenge. Unexpected cable faults lead to unplanned outages, increased SAIDI and SAIFI indices, emergency repair interventions, and substantial financial costs associated with fault localization, excavation, and service restoration. In urban cable networks, where access to infrastructure is limited and repair times are long, a single MV cable failure can affect a large number of customers and cause prolonged supply interruptions. Early detection of insulation degradation and partial discharge activity is therefore a key factor in preventing catastrophic failures and reducing outage duration through condition-based maintenance strategies.

MV cable with cross-linked polyethylene (XLPE) insulation is a sensitive component concerning the requirement for insulation homogeneity, including cracks, bubbles or gas pockets, which (due to lower permittivity and lower electrical strength) lead to the formation of electrical trees and, as a result, to local overheating, the formation of high-frequency (HF) currents, the

generation of UV radiation and insulation breakdown—that is, component failure and its malfunction [6–8].

These conditions are already prevented during the production of MV cables, when, using output tests, usually in the form of partial discharge (PD) measurements [9], a certain limit of apparent charge must not be exceeded (it depends on the distance of the measured cable, but usually the limit is a value in the order of lower pC units). The charge value is very low due to the large capacitance of the object (cable), making the measurement itself difficult.

Cable testing is performed using PD free component, after which the tested cable is connected to the test source utilizing an oil or water cable termination. Higher partial discharge values for the measured cable represent the above defects (bubbles, cracks), leading to a possible future failure [10]. It can be stated that the magnitude of the partial discharges of the cable is directly related to its service life (for a new cable) or for a used cable with a residual technical life. The same can be said for the so-called components of cable assemblies (cable terminations, adapters, connectors, couplings), which mainly depend on the quality of the technical design.

The requirement or maximum limit for these components is usually a value in the lower tens of pC. Cable networks do not generate their discharge activity (in a fault-free state, only a maximum of units of pC). But it is necessary to consider the generation of discharge activity in connected objects (power transformers, encapsulated switchboards), which is partially transmitted to cable networks. In terms of apparent charge values, it can be even higher tens to lower hundreds of pC [11–13].

This article focuses on the secondary use of PLC technology to detect partial discharges, which can reveal a problem with the cable itself or components. Unresolved discharge activity can cause a problem in the distribution system and, in the worst scenario, destruction or injury.

The introductory overview of current knowledge in the field of cable diagnostics and the use of PLC technologies is followed by Section 2, which summarizes current approaches and identifies the limitations of existing methods. Section 3 defines the research goals and the specific contributions of this work in the context of current scientific efforts. Section 4 describes the tested cable, the laboratory setup, and the method used for artificial PD generation. Sections 4.1 and 4.2 provide details on individual measurements, while Section 5 explains the process of acquiring communication parameters from BPL modems. The experimental findings are presented in Section 6, which is divided into three parts: measurements performed using inductive coupling, those using capacitive coupling, and an analysis of the effect of the coupling method on the sensitivity of PD detection. The broader implications of the results are then examined in Section 7. The article concludes with a summary of findings, recommendations for future research, and final remarks in Section 8.

The main contribution of this paper lies in the presentation of a systematic comparison of inductive and capacitive coupling in BPL communication with respect to partial discharge detection,

and in demonstrating the feasibility of using BPL technology for secondary purposes as an indicator of partial discharges.

2 | State-of-the-Art

The presentation [14] focuses on the pilot testing of PLC technology on the MV network in Barcelona. The topology consists of three rings, where a total of 70 substations are equipped with the technology. The author presents that before the cable problem, there was a noticeable change in the PLC channel capacity, after which the technology could also be used as a diagnostic tool.

The article [15] deals with the development of PLC modems with a throughput of 200 Mbps, which use OFDM modulation. The authors describe not only laboratory testing of these modems to verify their performance and impact on other devices, but also practical deployment in real conditions—specifically on MV and low voltage (LV) lines. The results of field tests confirm that these modems work reliably as a communication system on the existing electrical infrastructure. The article thus demonstrates the practical feasibility and performance of a high-speed PLC solution for use in energy distribution networks.

This article [16] deals with PLC from a regulatory perspective. The authors present the results of real-world measurements that were performed to verify the performance of PLC systems and to confirm the effectiveness of the interference suppression techniques implemented in the second generation of PLC technologies. In addition to the technical results themselves, the article also addresses regulatory issues, in particular the coexistence of PLC systems with other communication technologies that operate in the same frequency band of 1.7–80 MHz. That is, how PLC can operate without interfering with other services (e.g., radio or other data transmissions), and what requirements or restrictions this entails from a legislative and regulatory perspective.

Hashieh and Soukal [17] show a typical network in Egypt, where they use Corinex BPL modems. They point out a significant difference in communication when using modems without or with a filter. The improvement was almost twofold. The publication focuses primarily on testing PLC communication.

The authors [18] present a new method for detecting and locating cable insulation degradation (so-called water treeing) without the need to disconnect the voltage. The method uses nonlinear frequency analysis of signals from PLC (communication over electrical lines), because insulation degradation causes nonlinear behavior of the cable. By detecting these nonlinearities, the location of the damage can be determined. Simulations confirmed the effectiveness of the proposed approach, which has the potential for practical use in the diagnosis of cable systems.

Horvat et al. [19] represent the use of PLC technology for a last-mile solution for broadband deployment in rural areas instead of conventional local area network solutions. With a larger number of users, the problem of lower throughput arises.

The authors of [20] describe field testing of PLC communication with 200 Mbps modems in an LV test network. The aim was to verify the throughput and adaptability of the modems to

the physical characteristics of the channel and to evaluate their potential use at the MV level in the oil and gas industry. The experiments were performed on a 180-meter-long LV cable, where the resulting throughput was more than 100 Mbps.

The publication [21] focuses on the use of PLC technology in Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI) systems. The authors experimentally compared narrowband and broadband PLC technologies in conjunction with a smart meter. Tests of communication throughput and transmission range were performed under different conditions, without load and with load. The results showed that broadband PLC has higher throughput than narrowband, which is due to the larger bandwidth it uses. In terms of range, both technologies achieved comparable results—up to 1.5 km in laboratory conditions.

This work [22] focuses on the analysis of real-world measured channels in underground MV networks with the aim of better understanding the characteristics of the transmission environment for PLC. It focuses on the frequency band 2–40 MHz and metrics such as average attenuation, delay and coherent bandwidth. The results are used to derive models that help in the design of PLC technologies for demanding conditions in distribution networks.

The publication [23] focuses on the development of an insulation diagnostic method focused on measuring PD on MV cables. The aim was to monitor changes in PD characteristics during insulation aging and to interpret these changes to physical phenomena occurring inside defects. The results are based on long-term durability tests of cable samples in a high-voltage laboratory.

The article [24] deals with the use of broadband power line communication (BPL) at MV level in distribution networks. It discusses the specifics of this technology in comparison with narrowband communication at low voltage and domestic BPL systems. It focuses on differences like interference, requirements for throughput, redundancy and network topology. The authors propose a specially adapted communication protocol LOADng¹ for these applications, which brings significant advantages for diagnostics and operation of distribution networks.

In [25], authors investigate the influence of voltage frequency and shape on PD measurement using VLF power supply in MV networks. The influence of different VLF waveforms (sine, cosine-rectangular) on PD behavior in an XLPE cable sample with an artificial cavity was investigated experimentally and by simulation (COMSOL, MATLAB). The results show that the shape and frequency of the voltage significantly affect PD activity and that there is a good agreement between measurement and simulation. The results contribute to a better understanding of cable condition diagnostics using VLF-PD.

The publication [26] deals with the possibility of using existing PLC modems for PD detection in the insulation of medium voltage cables. The authors propose two techniques that allow detecting PD during signal demodulation in broadband PLC receivers. These methods are based on the changes that PD causes at certain carrier frequencies used in OFDM modulation. The advantage is that only a firmware modification is required, without the need to install new hardware. The article is theoretical, but

simulation results confirm the ability of the proposed methods to detect various types of partial discharges. The effect of mutual interference between channels is also taken into account and measures to improve detection are proposed.

Also Huo et al. [27] presents an autonomous method for diagnosing the condition of distribution cables using existing PLC modems. The authors focus on (paper-insulated lead-covered) PILC cables, which are susceptible to thermal aging. Changes in dielectric properties caused by degradation are also reflected in the PLC channel, but the differences in transmission characteristics are not significant enough for manual diagnostics. Therefore, the authors propose a solution based on machine learning that can reliably estimate the level of degradation even under different loads. The results show high accuracy and the authors believe that this method will enable low-cost and autonomous monitoring of cable condition without the need for specialized personnel or equipment.

The publication [28] focuses on a method for diagnosing LV cables using broadband impedance spectroscopy, which uses frequency response analysis of the channel and can be implemented via broadband PLC modems. The aim is to enable online diagnostics of the cable condition and estimation of its remaining service life. Laboratory tests show that the proposed method is capable of detecting and locating faults in LV cables. The proposed algorithm is capable of locating the defect within approximately two meters.

This paper [29] deals with the analysis of impulse noise in household PLC systems, which significantly affects their performance. The authors argue that common characteristics, such as the average power spectral density (PSD), are not enough to understand the complexity of these noises, and therefore propose the use of spectral entropy. Specifically, they show that Shannon's spectral entropy can quantify the degree of regularity in the spectral distribution of impulse noises. This approach could contribute to a more accurate identification of noise sources, which would help to more reliable diagnostics and improvement of PLC systems.

The authors of [30] emphasize that for reliable diagnostics of interference effects in broadband communication systems, it is important to accurately characterize impulse interference. Such interference, originating from household appliances, reaches the modem via various paths through the electrical network, which increases its diversity. The authors point out that due to the influence of diverse household electrical installations, it is important to first remove the influence of transmission paths for analyzing impulse interference—specifically, they propose to use deconvolution to be able to faithfully characterize the interference in the time domain directly from what arrives at the receiver.

This paper [31] is devoted to the comparison of on-line and off-line PD measurements on MV cables. Twelve differently connected cables were assembled into a loop that was loaded with nominal voltage and current. Daily temperature cycles were applied using toroidal transformers and on-line PD monitoring was performed during these cycles. After a certain number of cycles, the cables

were tested separately off-line at different voltages. The results showed that the formation of a defect in XLPE cables was detected earlier by on-line PD measurements. Off-line tests confirmed the presence of a defect only after a longer exposure to temperature changes. PD activity during the cycles was random and gradually weakened, while off-line measurements after the cycles helped to identify the defects.

Hopfer et al. [32] use BPL communication to determine the technical condition of a cable. They used initial measurements in laboratory conditions, when they loaded an XLPE cable in an oven and then examined its transmission properties. In the case of discharge activity, they present only three different states that do not define the size of the charges (no/weak PD, medium PD, and heavy PD). For field measurements, they use BPL modems based on the IEEE 1901 standard and captured signal to noise ratio (SNR) values every 15 min.—for 7 months. The 15-min period is too long to be able to capture a partial discharge that lasts in the order of units to hundreds of nanoseconds. It is highly unlikely that this configuration would detect discharge activity. The method can be applied for comparison, but more variables enter into it, such as weather, season, network status, topology, etc.

Huo et al. [33] presents a low-cost method for remote monitoring of electrical cables in smart grid networks using already installed PLC modems. The authors propose a machine learning-based framework that performs automatic cable diagnostics—classifying the aging profile, assessing the degree of degradation and locating potential faults. The diagnostics uses joint-time-frequency domain reflectometry (JTFR), which allow new diagnostic features to be extracted. Simulation results show high accuracy in detection and prediction, while the modem firmware can be easily updated. The proposed solution thus allows PLCs to be used not only for communication, but also as sensors for continuous cable monitoring and early fault prevention.

Reference [34] deals with the use of HomePlug AV (HPAV) technology for powerline communication in local computer networks and for connecting network devices, as a solution to the problem of the limited range of standard Ethernet over twisted pair, which typically does not exceed a distance of 100 meters. Thus, communication takes place over an Ethernet cable, not over a standard LV/MV cable.

The research group Mlynek et al. [35] presents the throughput performance of BPL communication with modems with the IEEE 1901 standard on a real topology. The communication was tested by simulating data traffic that commonly occurs between substations (IEC 60870-5-104, MODBUS or IEC-61850).

Esterl et al. [36] deal with PD measurements in Direct Current (DC) cable systems, especially those with XLPE insulation. As DC cables are becoming more common, there is growing interest in their diagnostics using PD. However, it turns out that partial discharges occur much less frequently under DC voltage than under AC, which reduces the effectiveness of this diagnostics. The work investigated artificial faults in cable joints on non-commercial DC-XLPE cables under DC voltages up to 180 kV. It was found that the discharge frequency is mainly affected by the cable temperature and the voltage magnitude.

This paper [37] focuses on the forensic analysis of MV polymer cable faults, which play a key role in modern power systems. It presents diagnostic electrical methods such as insulation resistance measurement, Alternating current (AC) hipot and PD measurements, as well as non-destructive procedures such as visual inspection, optical microscopy and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). Special emphasis is placed on the recommended order of these methods depending on the type of failure. The study shows how DSC can be used to determine the thermal history of a polymer cable and identify possible causes of its overheating. The paper provides practical guidance for network operators in determining the causes of faults in the field.

The authors of the article [38] use PLC technology as a tool for monitoring PD by means of a drop in the throughput rate in the voltage phase dependence. This is a laboratory measurement, where partial discharges in the order of nC were detected, after which these values indicate a highly degraded cable and at the same time this value can be detected by most methods and sensors.

Another publication [39] is very similar to the first two, since the author is the same research group. The laboratory measurement was verified by field measurements, where the PDMS-PLC (PD detection method and monitoring system) method is introduced. According to the authors, the method was able to detect partial discharges. However, discharge activity could be detected up to around 900 pC, which is still approximately 10 times higher than what commonly available methods and sensors are capable of capturing.

The article [40] presents a non-invasive method for estimating impedance in a PLC network, which uses only subsequent voltage measurements and various loads on the receiving side of the PLC modem. The advantage is that it can be used with existing PLC modems without the need for hardware modifications. The method has been verified by simulations and practical tests, while effects such as noise, digitization or time synchronization have been analyzed. The results are comparable to reference measurements using a vector network analyzer, and therefore the method is considered promising. Further tests on real modems in the network are planned.

Seri et al. [41] investigate the differences between PD measurements at VLF and at power frequencies. Although the standards (IEC 60502, IEEE 400.2) allow the use of VLF for testing MV and HV cable insulation, the results of PD tests at VLF can differ. Using a simple mathematical model and experiments on XLPE and polypropylene insulators, it was demonstrated that the electrostatic charge on the internal surfaces of defects plays a significant role in influencing the field distribution and the value of the PDIV. Depending on the material, the discharge inception voltage at VLF can be significantly higher or lower than at 50/60 Hz.

Huo et al. [42] present a method for diagnosing cable conditions using PLC modems and machine learning. Unlike previous studies that used only synthetic data, the authors use S-parameter measurements of real equipment to create more realistic training data. This data is then used to train models that can reliably detect

cable faults even under varying loads. Results from laboratory tests confirm the effectiveness of this approach.

The paper [43] proposes a comprehensive diagnostic solution for monitoring railway infrastructure, specifically for detecting soft faults in underground railway cables. The authors first demonstrate the feasibility of a fault detection and localization method based on orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM) reflectometry, which they implement using software-defined radios. Based on a practical implementation and measurement campaign, they propose a composite method that combines multiple diagnostic approaches. The result is the calculation of a so-called cable health index using a Bayesian framework, which indicates the degree of cable degradation over its lifetime. The performance of the proposed solution is verified based on real-world measurements.

This article [44] extends the research from the previous citation. The authors created an environment where they try to simulate a typical substation with a gas-insulated switch, cable and transformer. The work lacks a description of the cable and the method of injecting partial discharges, as well as how much charge was generated and at what frequency.

The researchers [45] conducted long-term measurements on a real network in a distribution substation, where they collected data for 40 days. Their PDMS method revealed that the permeability decreases in the 1st and 3rd quadrants. Their method is therefore suitable for detecting PD in places other than laboratory conditions. However, no analysis has been carried out on where PD occurs, what values it takes, and whether there is a problem in a given location or how to solve the problem.

The publication [46] deals with the comparison of different voltage waveforms used for PD measurements in MV cable systems. PD measurements are used to detect local defects in insulation or cable terminations that can lead to accelerated aging. In a laboratory study, the sensitivities of measurements using 60 Hz alternating voltage, damped alternating current and very low frequency (VLF) were compared. The detection capability, localization and noise level were evaluated, as well as the values of the discharge initiation (PDIV) and discharge extinction (PDEV) voltages. The results show the influence of the voltage waveform on the sensitivity and accuracy of PD diagnostics.

Musil et al. [47] mentions the issue of PLC communication mainly in the area of interference. In a real topology, a distributor had a problem in a residential area with reading smart electricity meters. The authors localized the interference and proposed a total of four different solutions or recommendations.

The paper [48] deals with a new method for detecting and locating faults in an electrical network using PLC devices. The key element is the real-time impedance estimation based on the channel frequency response (CFR) measured by the PLC receiver. The method uses transmission line modeling, variational modal decomposition signal processing, and machine learning to identify impedance changes that signal faults. Simulations show that

the proposed approach achieves high accuracy, especially for low-impedance faults, with a localization error of less than 2.13%.

Lemmerz et al. [49] is looking for a non-destructive method for detecting very small defects in cable insulation that are not reliably detected by conventional PD tests or hot oil tests. The study focuses on the use of ultrasonic technology for detecting defects in XLPE insulation of MV and HV cables. The samples were provided with artificial defects of up to 0.1 mm in size and subsequently scanned by an automated system. The results show that defects larger than 0.4 mm are visible in C-scan, while smaller defects (up to 0.1 mm) can be identified in B-scan. The ultrasonic method thus appears to be a promising tool for accurate and rapid detection of small internal defects in cable insulation.

Liang et al. [50] present an advanced, non-invasive diagnostic system using PLC technology to detect insulation faults in distribution networks. The authors propose a new approach that tracks the evolution of cable parameters from initial degradation (water treeing) to insulation failure. Using visual encoding of CFR by the Markov transition field method and neural networks with an attention mechanism, they can detect even small changes in cable behavior with high accuracy (<98%), which allows for early identification of faults even in complex networks.

Table 1 is divided into a total of nine columns. The first column of the table (ref.) is the citation of the article from which the information on the content of the reference is primarily taken. The second column (authors) indicates the first author. The third column (year) refers to the year of publication of the article. The fourth column (purpose) indicates the primary direction of the article; the highest frequency is represented by “Cable line diagnostics” and “PLC performance test”. The next column represents whether a simulation is designed, or measurements were performed in the laboratory or the field, or a mathematical model was presented. Columns six to nine are mainly marked ✓ or ✗ and indicate whether the article measures/calculates with a medium voltage cable, uses data throughput, determines the health/condition of the cable, or detects partial discharges.

Based on this comparison table, it is clear that most publications have only a minor overlap with this article. The publications focus on determining the performance of PLC devices where throughput is of interest. Still, few measurements are performed in the laboratory or the field on medium voltage cables. Cable line diagnostics has the second highest frequency, but the comparison shows that either throughput or partial discharge detection is used.

Only one publication [26] meets all four criteria, but this publication focuses on the use of OFDM modulation for partial discharge detection. The authors performed a simulation, where they conclude that for long-range PDs it is more appropriate to use the normalized correlation detector (NCD), while for low-energy PDs the zero crossing detector (ZCD) is better. In cases of short distances and high energy, PDs can be detected effectively by both methods, while their performance depends on the specific SNR level.

This paper focuses on PD detection using PLC-BPL communication under laboratory conditions and examines the influence of

capacitive and inductive coupling. Investigate the effect of PD on the XLPE cable. All of this is a secondary use of PLC technology.

3 | Research Motivation and Contribution

The increasing use of distributed energy sources and the requirement for robust smart grid infrastructure make more reliable and cost-effective diagnostic methods for MV cable systems necessary. PD activity is a widely recognised indicator of insulation degradation, which often precedes critical failures. However, conventional PD measurement techniques usually require specialised equipment and test setups, and often involve offline conditions, making continuous field monitoring of cable condition impractical.

Meanwhile, PLC/BPL is increasingly being used for network automation and data transmission purposes. These systems interact with the physical condition of the cable because throughput quality is affected by impedance mismatches, attenuation, and electromagnetic interference, all of which can be influenced by insulation defects or PD activity.

This research is motivated by the hypothesis that BPL communication parameters can serve as indirect indicators of emerging dielectric faults and PD activity. Repurposing BPL modems as diagnostic sensors as well as communication devices could enable the implementation of a continuous, cost-effective, non-invasive monitoring solution.

The main contributions of this work are as follows:

- Experimental demonstration of the influence of PD activity on BPL communication parameters (e.g., SNR, Tonemap, other parameters described in 5).
- Laboratory validation using a real MV cable segment and calibrated PD measurement equipment, ensuring controlled and repeatable testing conditions.
- Using the available BPL communication parameters, PD can be detected directly from operational communication data. This approach enables the development of a hybrid diagnostic method that integrates conventional and communication-based measurements, significantly improving the capability for early and reliable fault detection.
- Analytical exploration and demonstration of BPL technology as a dual-purpose tool-enabling both data communication and on-line diagnostics in MV distribution networks.
- Contribution to the scientific community through the publication of an open dataset [51], which can support further studies, enable the development of advanced diagnostic algorithms, and serve as a benchmark for comparative analysis of similar measurements.

Unlike previous studies, which have focused primarily on modelling BPL signals or have relied on simulated PD scenarios, this study presents results based on controlled, high-voltage laboratory measurements using real cables and equipment. This bridges the gap between theoretical modelling and practical application.

TABLE 1 | Overview and comparison of selected literature on PLC diagnostics in power cables.

Ref.	Authors	Year	Purpose	Execution	MV cable	Throughput	Cable health	PD detection
[14]	Comabella	2005	PLC pilot test	FM	✓	✓	✗	✗
[15]	Matsuo and Maekawa	2005	PLC performance test	FM	✓+LV	✓	✗	✗
[16]	Tomimura and Vellano	2008	PLC performance test	FM	✓+LV	✗	✗	✗
[17]	Hashiesh and Soukal	2009	Noise filters	FM	✓	✓	✗	✗
[18]	Chen et al.	2012	Cable line diagnostics	MM/S	unk.	✗	✓	✗
[19]	Horvat et al.	2012	PLC as a last-mile hybrid solution	LM	✗	✗	✗	✗
[20]	Castor et al.	2014	PLC performance test	LM	✗	✓	✗	✗
[21]	Sangsuwan et al.	2014	PLC performance test	LM	✗	✓	✗	✗
[22]	Versolatto et al.	2014	Noise analysis	SA	✓	✓	✗	✗
[23]	Ahmed et al.	2016	Cable line diagnostics with PD – VLF	LM	✓	✗	✓	✓
[24]	Llano et al.	2016	PLC performance test	FM	✓	✓	✗	✗
[25]	Gouda et al.	2017	Cable line diagnostics with PD – VLF	S/LM	✓	✗	✓	✓
[26]	Granado et al.	2018	PD detection via OFDM	MM/S	✓	✓	✓	✓
[27]	Huo et al.	2018	Cable line diagnostics	MM+S	✓+LV	✗	✓	✗
[28]	Poluektov et al.	2018	Cable line diagnostics	LM	✗	✗	✓	✗
[29]	Singh et al.	2018	Noise analysis	S	unk.	✗	✗	✗
[30]	Singh et al.	2018	Noise analysis	S	unk.	✗	✗	✗
[31]	Borghetto et al.	2019	On/off-line PD monitoring	S	✓+HV	✗	✓	✓
[32]	Hopfer et al.	2019	Analysis	FM	✓+LV	✗	✓	✓
[33]	Huo et al.	2019	Cable line diagnostics	MM+S	✓+LV	✗	✓	✗
[34]	Merkulov et al.	2019	PLC over twisted pair	LM	✗	✓	✗	✗
[35]	Mlynek et al.	2019	PLC performance test	FM	✓	✓	✗	✗
[36]	Esterl et al.	2020	Cable line diagnostics with PD - DC ramp	LM	✓	✗	✓	✓
[37]	Jahromi et al.	2020	Cable line diagnostics (DSC ^a)	LM	✓	✗	✓	✓
[38]	Kakimoto et al.	2020	Cable line diagnostics	LM	✗	✓	✓	✓
[39]	Kakimoto et al.	2020	Cable line diagnostics	LM+FM	✗	✓	✓	✓
[40]	Righini et al.	2020	Cable line diagnostics	S/LM	✓+LV	✗	✓	✗
[41]	Seri et al.	2020	Cable line diagnostics with PD – VLF	LM	✓+HV	✗	✓	✓
[42]	Huo et al.	2021	Cable line diagnostics	MM+S	✓+LV	✗	✓	✗
[43]	Vijay et al.	2021	Rail Cable line diagnostics	FM	✓	✗	✓	✗
[44]	Houdai et al.	2022	Cable line diagnostics	LM+FM	✗	✓	✓	✓
[45]	Houdai et al.	2022	Cable line diagnostics	FM	✗	✓	✓	✓
[46]	Jahromi et al.	2022	PD measurement	LM	✓	✗	✓	✓
[47]	Musil et al.	2023	Noise localization	FM	✗	✓	✗	✗
[48]	Liang et al.	2023	Cable line diagnostics (CFR)	S	✓	✗	✓	✗

(Continues)

TABLE 1 | (Continued)

Ref.	Authors	Year	Purpose	Execution	MV cable	Throughput	Cable health	PD detection
[49]	Lemmerz et al.	2024	Cable line diagnostics (ultrasonic)	LM	✓+HV	✗	✓	✗
[50] ^b	Liang et al.	2025	Cable line diagnostics (CFR and MTF ^c)	S	✓	✗	✓	✗

aDSC – differential scanning calorimetry

bThe publication is released as Early Access only.

cMTF – Markov transition field

LM – laboratory measurement, FM – field measurement, MM – mathematical model, S – simulation, SA – statistics and analysis.

unk. – unknown.

FIGURE 1 | High voltage laboratory is part of The Department of Electrical Power Engineering, Brno University of Technology is a part of Center for Research and Utilization of Renewable Energy (CVVOZEPowerLab) and Center for New Technologies for Mechanical Engineering (NETME). Measurement with increasing voltage. PD generation using overvoltage.

4 | Experimental Methodology for PD Detection in Medium Voltage Cable

For laboratory testing, a MV cable with the designation (N)A2X(F)2Y 1x150RM/25 20.8/36 kV manufactured by NKT s.r.o. cables from 2017 was used. The total length of the cable was 22 meters, see Figure 1.

The initial measurement was performed under voltage, after which the cable was terminated with Haefely CTT-350 water cable terminals, the Haefely/Hipotronics AC Test System 300 kV, 1 A was used as the power source. For PD measurement, the Hipotronics DDX 7000 and DDX 8003 with a Haefely CIC-300 1 nF coupling capacitor were used. The galvanic method and the galvanic method with pulse discrimination—two channels were used.

BPL modems based on the IEEE 1901-2010 standard, operating in the 1.8–30 MHz band, were used for communication. The primary parameter monitored was throughput, with emphasis placed on its variations over time rather than on the absolute values achieved in either communication direction.

The throughput was established using two PLC/BPL modems that injected the signal into the MV cable via inductive and capacitive couplers. Communication parameters were analyzed using the iPerf tool, while a Python script simultaneously retrieved status data from the modems. The iPerf tool operated with a measurement interval of 1 s, whereas data from the modems were collected every 10 s.

The measurement was divided into two parts:

FIGURE 2 | Workplace in a voltage-free state when generating PD using Tettex KAL 9520 into the (N)A2X(F)2Y cable.

- First measurement with linear voltage increase in the range 0–100 kV is described in the Section 4.1.
- Second measurement with cable in de-energized state is described in the Section 4.2.

The measurements were focused on evaluating the impact of partial discharge activity on selected BPL communication parameters and analysing their correlation with the PD level under different coupling conditions.

4.1 | First Measurement: Overvoltage

In the initial PD measurements on the tested sample, no discharge activity was recorded at voltages up to 24 kV, which can be interpreted as the absence of local weak spots in the insulation system and at the same time as evidence of sufficient dielectric strength in this area of electrical stress.

After exceeding this threshold level, partial discharges occur with an increase in the discharge charge, while the dependence of the charge size on the applied voltage does not show a linear course. In the range of 30–70 kV, a slight, quasi-linear growth of the discharge charge can be observed with local fluctuations, which may be related to the randomness of the discharge processes in the microstructure of the insulation. In this voltage range, discharges probably occur at a smaller number of weak spots or edge inhomogeneities, while the system still retains the ability to suppress or stabilize discharges partially.

However, from the value of 80 kV, a sharp increase in the discharge charge is noticeable (from units of nC to the lower tens of nC), which can be interpreted as a transition to a regime of significantly increased discharge activity (incipient

phase of degradation). This increase signals that more discharge channels have been activated, or the existing ionization paths have been enlarged, which increases the intensity of the discharge pulses. Above the value of 90 kV up to 100 kV, the discharge activity already reaches significant values (up to 15 nC), which may indicate an approaching risk of breakdown or progressive degradation of the insulation system.

The overall character of the dependence of the discharge charge on the magnitude of the applied voltage is therefore nonlinear, with an initial threshold delay, a quasi-linear region of moderate growth, and a subsequent sharp expansion of the discharge activity at higher voltage levels. This course corresponds to the typical behavior of a dielectric system with gradual activation of discharge centers and a transition to a high discharge density regime.

4.2 | Second Measurement: Cable in De-Energized State

Further measurements were guided by the initial observation that no PD occurred below an applied voltage of 30 kV. This suggests that under standard operating conditions, at the nominal voltage of 22 kV, no discharge activity should be present. Therefore, any occurrence of PD during normal operation would indicate an abnormal condition, potentially caused by cable degradation or insulation defects—the following experiments aimed to detect such abnormal activity under otherwise standard operating conditions. To simulate fault scenarios, the cable was in a de-energized state while PD were externally induced using a Tettex KAL 9520 partial discharge generator. The generator allows the generation of discharges in the range of 0.1 pC to 50,000 pC. The steepness of the front of one pulse is in the range of 4–5 ns. The connection is shown in Figure 2.

From a measurement perspective, three nominal values were selected that affected broadband communication:

- 50 pC–Below the resolution limit of commonly available PD detectors.
- 100 pC–Beginning of the resolution of PD detection by commonly available PD detectors.
- 1,000 pC–A significantly higher PD magnitude was applied to ensure an observable impact on BPL communication parameters in case lower PD levels produced no measurable effects.

5 | Measurement Setup for BPL Communication and Parameter Acquisition

As previously mentioned, PLC/BPL technology is primarily used as an alternative communication method by distribution companies, enabling communication between substations through Distribution Transformer Station (DTS) links connected to the SCADA system. This setup serves purposes such as automation, remote control, and measurement.

To detect PD and assess the technical condition of the cable throughout the entire measurement period, all available parameters provided by the modems were utilized:

A–Downstream (Data Download Speed)

This parameter indicates the current data throughput from the server to the measuring device (terminal). It reflects the effective network throughput for receiving data and is a key indicator of connection quality. The downstream value may vary depending on network load, interference, or changes in the modulation scheme. Higher values correspond to greater available bandwidth for incoming data. It is measured in megabits per second (Mbps) at one-second intervals.

Partial discharge activity can influence the measured download speed, with increased PD levels leading to a reduction in download throughput.

B–Upstream (Data Upload Speed)

Upstream denotes the current data throughput from the measuring device (terminal) to the server. Similar to downstream, higher values indicate better capacity for outgoing data transmission. Variations in this value can result from signal degradation, interference, or transmitter power control. The value is expressed in megabits per second (Mbps) and is recorded every second.

Partial discharge activity can influence the measured upload speed, with increased PD levels leading to a reduction in upload throughput.

C–Measurement Time

A standardized timestamp is used to synchronize measurements between the terminal and the server. This ensures accurate temporal alignment of recorded data, enabling reliable time series

analysis. The timestamp is recorded every second using the format YYYY-MM-DD HH:MM:SS.

D–CLCR Link Capacity

The CLCR parameter represents the theoretical maximum capacity of the transmission channel at a given moment. It is derived from modulation parameters and the current state of the transmission line. A low CLCR value may indicate reduced transmission efficiency due to interference or unfavorable line conditions. The range is from 0 to 1,–800 Mbps, with measurements taken every 10 s.

Bit loading estimate (BLE): For unicast MPDUs and broadcast MPDUs transmitted by the original source, the bit loading estimate (BLE) is an 8-bit field that represents the number of user data bits (i.e., data bits before FEC - encoding) that can be carried on the channel per microsecond. It takes into account the overhead due to the cyclic prefix and FEC, but does not include the overhead associated with the protocol data unit (PPDU) format (e.g., delimiter) and inter frame spacing (IFS) [52].

The BLE shall be calculated using the formula:

$$\text{BLE} = \frac{\text{BitsPerOFDMSymbol} \times R \times (1 - P_{b,\text{error}})}{T_s} \quad (3)$$

where:

- T_s is the symbol length in μs (including the guard interval – GI).
- R is the forward error correction (FEC) code rate.
- $P_{b,\text{error}}$ is the bit error probability prior to FEC.

The parameter $P_{b,\text{error}}$ should be selected based on the expected bit error rate of the link at the moment a new tone map is generated. This value remains fixed until replaced by a new tone map.

ECLBT Link BLE TX (Number of BLE Packets Transmitted)

CLBT indicates the number of bit load estimate (BLE) packets successfully transmitted from the terminal to the server. This metric is important for evaluating the stability and capacity of BLE-based communication. Values typically range from 8 to 200 and are recorded every 10 s.

F–CLBR Link BLE RX (Number of BLE Packets Received)

CLBR reflects the number of BLE packets successfully received from the server or peer device. A drop in this value may signal transmission issues, interference, or channel congestion. Like CLBT, the values range from 8 to 200 and are measured every 10 s.

G, H, I–RTSS (Number of Successfully Sent RTS Requests in 10, 30, and 60 s)

RTSS indicates the number of *Request-To-Send* (RTS) messages successfully transmitted during the specified time intervals:

- **RTSS 10:** Successful RTS requests in the last 10 s.

- **RTSS 30:** Successful RTS requests in the last 30 s.
- **RTSS 60:** Successful RTS requests in the last 60 s.

Higher RTSS values suggest active communication, while lower counts may point to media access issues or interference.

J, K, L—RTSF (Number of Failed RTS Requests in 10, 30, and 60 s)

RTSF tracks the number of RTS requests that failed, that is, sent without receiving a response. It is evaluated across the same intervals:

- **RTSF 10:** Failed RTS requests in the last 10 s.
- **RTSF 30:** Failed RTS requests in the last 30 s.
- **RTSF 60:** Failed RTS requests in the last 60 s.

High RTSF values can indicate congestion, interference, or link instability.

O, P, Q—DATS (Number of Data Frames Sent in 10, 30, and 60 s)

DATS measures the total number of data frames transmitted over specified intervals:

- **DATS 10:** Frames sent in the last 10 s.
- **DATS 30:** Frames sent in the last 30 s.
- **DATS 60:** Frames sent in the last 60 s.

Lower DATS values may signal transmission delays or reduced activity due to congestion.

R, S, T—DATR (Number of Data Frames Received in 10, 30, and 60 s)

DATR represents the number of data frames successfully received within the given time frames:

- **DATR 10:** Frames received in the last 10 s.
- **DATR 30:** Frames received in the last 30 s.
- **DATR 60:** Frames received in the last 60 s.

Significant drops in received frames compared to sent ones may suggest packet loss or unstable connectivity.

U—VS_GET_AMP_MAP (Transmission Amplitude Map)

This parameter provides detailed information on the amplitude levels across individual transmission frequencies. It enables in-depth analysis of signal attenuation and is critical for diagnosing losses at specific frequency components.

V—VS_GET_SNR

SNR indicates the signal quality for each carrier frequency. Higher values correspond to better transmission conditions,

whereas lower values suggest potential interference or degradation.

W—VS_GET_TONEMAP (Modulation Scheme)

The tonemap displays the modulation schemes applied to individual carriers. The choice of modulation depends on the real-time transmission conditions and directly affects the channel capacity and reliability.

X—VS_GET_TONEMASK (Carrier Frequency Usage)

This parameter identifies which carrier frequencies are actively used and which are excluded from transmission—either due to regulatory constraints or detected interference. It provides insight into spectrum usage and possible notching behavior.

The list of these parameters is specific to a particular type of BPL modem. However, most modems based on the IEEE 1901-2010 standard support a very similar set of measurement parameters. These were chosen primarily because they are capable of describing, at least to some extent, the current conditions and activity on the cable from a broader perspective.

Each measurement cycle lasted 20 min. The first 10 min. were reserved for initialization and for the BPL modems to adapt to the characteristics of the connected MV cable. After this stabilization period, the PD generator was activated and remained in operation for approximately 5 min. At the 15-min. mark, the generator was switched off, and the system was left to recover for the remaining 5 min., allowing for observation of the post-disturbance behavior of communication parameters.

Measurements were conducted separately using inductive and capacitive couplers to enable a comparative analysis of how different coupling methods influence the throughput behavior under PD conditions.

In the experimental setup, the PD generator was connected with one terminal to the cable conductor and the other to the metallic shield. This configuration was deliberately chosen to simulate localized dielectric stress, as typically observed under real fault conditions in MV distribution systems. Such stress conditions often arise due to insulation degradation between the core and the shield, caused by factors such as moisture ingress, mechanical damage, or aging of insulating materials. Moreover, this core-to-shield arrangement represents the most probable path for partial discharges to occur in degraded cable systems. Therefore, it was deemed appropriate to simulate and evaluating the impact of discharge activity on BPL communication parameters.

6 | Results

After initial verification using initialization measurements, it was proven that no PD occurs in the cable under investigation when an operating voltage of up to 22 kV is applied. These measurements were performed with a fully terminated cable using water terminations, and the measurement discharges were monitored using a standard phase test procedure. The results

Bidirectional throughput during **inductive** coupling 50, 100 and 1,000 pC, **shield-to-core** injection

FIGURE 3 | Measured bidirectional throughput during **inductive** coupling with **shield-to-core** partial discharge injection (50, 100, and 1,000 pC). The discharges were active from 600 to 900 s.

were in line with the assumptions and demonstrated good discharge strength of the cable in its original technical condition.

Based on these findings, further experiments were performed, this time at zero supply voltage, to analyze the effect of PD on the communication capabilities of the BPL system. The signal for BPL communication was applied to the cable in two ways—inductively and capacitively. The PD signal was generated by a discharge generator with adjustable discharge energy (in the range of 50, 100 and 1,000 pC) and was injected into the system from one side of the cable into the core and at the opposite end into the shielding. The PD connection was performed as the most probable for real parasitic phenomena in the event of an insulation failure.

The measurements were always performed for 1200 s, with:

- The first 600 s were reserved for stabilizing the BPL communication without interference.
- At time 600 s, the PD generator was activated and the state was maintained for 300 s (up to 900 s).
- The remaining 300 s were used to observe the system recovery after the PD was turned off.

During each experiment, the bidirectional throughput in Mbps was continuously monitored using the iPerf3 tool. Each graph represents measurements with three discharge levels: 50, 100 and 1,000 pC.

6.1 | Measurement Using Inductive Coupling

Figure 3 shows the bidirectional throughput over time when a BPL signal is applied using inductive coupling. In this connection, the modem was connected to the cable line via an inductive coil placed outside the cable shield, that is, without direct galvanic contact. This method represents a contactless variant of how a BPL data signal can be applied to the cable.

The PD generator was connected to the free end of the cable using alligator clips—one was connected to the shield and the other to the cable core. This configuration creates a fault simulating internal discharge activity in the insulation, which affects both basic conductive layers.

The measurement was carried out for 1,200 s, with the discharge generator being active between 600 and 900 s (the interval is marked with red dashed lines with the labels “PD ON” and “PD OFF”). During this interval, discharges of 50 pC, 100 pC and 1,000 pC are generated. A separate curve is plotted on the graph for each of these cases.

It is clear from the figure that the presence of discharges has a significant effect on the throughput of the cable line, especially at higher levels of the fault signal:

- At 50 pC, there is a slight decrease in throughput, but the system remains stable, with minimal outages.
- Discharges of 100 pC cause more noticeable degradation—throughput fluctuates between 40 and 50 Mbps and shows periodic fluctuations.
- The highest discharge level of 1,000 pC causes a dramatic decrease in throughput, in some places up to the limit of 10–15 Mbps, and the system shows significant instability.

After the discharges are turned off, the BPL throughput gradually recovers, but the return is not immediate and depends on the previous load. The results clearly show that even with a contactless connection, discharge activity has a significant disruptive effect on BPL communication.

6.2 | Measurement Using Capacitive Coupling

Figure 4 shows the measurement results in a configuration where the BPL modem is connected to the cable by capacitive coupling. In this case, the data signal is supplied galvanically—by a direct electrical connection between the modem and the

FIGURE 4 | Measured bidirectional throughput during **capacitive** coupling with **shield-to-core** partial discharge injection (50, 100, and 1,000 pC). The discharges were active from 600 to 900 s.

cable conductors. This connection ensures higher signal quality and stability, but can also be more sensitive to external disturbances.

The discharges were generated, as in the previous case, using alligator clips that were connected to the end of the conductor—between the shield and the cable core. The discharge generator was active in the period 600–900 s, with three levels of discharge activity: 50, 100 and 1,000 pC.

The throughput curve shows that:

- At the lowest discharge level (50 pC) the throughput is almost untouched, remains above 60 Mbps without significant fluctuations.
- At 100 pC, a slight deterioration in stability can be observed, but the throughput does not drop below 45–50 Mbps.
- At 1,000 pC, the disturbing effect is more noticeable—the throughput fluctuates in the range of 20–35 Mbps, but the course is less fluctuating than in the inductive variant.

The recovery course after the discharges are turned off is particularly interesting. In the case of capacitive coupling, the system quickly returns to the initial operating state, without any noticeable reverberation of the previous disturbance. This suggests that the galvanic connection has a better ability to adapt to sudden disturbances, or is less susceptible to persistent phenomena such as modem adaptation or loss of synchronization.

From an overall perspective, it can be stated that the capacitive coupling exhibits higher resistance to discharges than the inductive variant under the same conditions.

6.3 | Effect of Coupling Method on PD Detection Sensitivity

The coupling mechanisms exhibit frequency-dependent behavior determined by their physical principles. Capacitive coupling

provides more efficient signal injection at higher frequencies due to the decreasing capacitive reactance, whereas inductive coupling is primarily limited by the mutual inductance and core characteristics, resulting in reduced coupling efficiency at higher frequencies. This frequency-selective behavior influences the sensitivity of individual BPL parameters to partial discharge activity and was considered in the interpretation of the measurement results.

Figure 5 shows a direct comparison of both BPL modem connection methods—inductive and capacitive—at the same PD size of 100 pC. The goal was to objectively evaluate how different couplings affect the throughput quality with identical external interference.

With capacitive connection (blue curve), the throughput is more stable, fluctuating slightly in the range of 50–60 Mbps. With inductive connection (red curve), the interference is more pronounced, the throughput drops below 40 Mbps and the signal shows higher instability.

From the above comparison, it follows that capacitive coupling provides higher throughput stability and greater resistance to interference caused by discharge activity. From the point of view of communication quality and robustness, capacitive modem connection would therefore be the preferred option.

On the other hand, if we were to consider using BPL technology as a tool for monitoring partial discharges during operation, that is, as a method of indirect detection of degradation phenomena in insulation, inductive coupling may be more advantageous. Due to its higher sensitivity and more pronounced response to discharge activity, it could enable more reliable detection of faults, even at lower discharge levels.

In addition, inductive connection has the advantage of being non-invasive—there is no need to interrupt or galvanically connect the lines, which is often technically and safety-wise advantageous in real operation. From this point of view, the inductive method could therefore be preferred for on-line diagnostics of

FIGURE 5 | Measured bidirectional throughput during **capacitive and inductive** coupling with **shield-to-core** partial discharge injection (100 pC). The discharges were active from 600 to 900 s.

the insulation condition through the analysis of changes in the BPL throughput.

The higher sensitivity of inductive coupling to partial discharge activity can be explained by the impulsive nature of discharge phenomena. Partial discharges generate short-duration current pulses, which are accompanied by transient magnetic fields surrounding the cable. Inductive coupling responds directly to these magnetic field variations, making it particularly sensitive to discharge activity occurring inside the cable insulation. In contrast, capacitive coupling is mainly influenced by variations of the electric field and voltage. Due to the localized character of partial discharges and the shielding effect of the cable insulation and semiconductive layers, the associated electric field disturbances are less effectively transferred to the capacitive coupling interface. Consequently, inductive coupling exhibits a stronger response to partial discharge activity, whereas capacitive coupling provides more stable conditions for data transmission.

7 | Discussion

An important lesson learned from this study is that when deploying BPL technology, it is crucial to ensure the collection of communication parameters such as those described in Section 5 (e.g., SNR, Link Capacity, BLE). These parameters can serve not only as relevant indicators of cable health and its long-term degradation, but also as a potential tool for on-line partial discharge detection, especially in cases of sudden deviations reflected in throughput performance.

In real distribution networks operating under normal background noise conditions, the detection of low-amplitude partial discharge activity based on a single communication metric can be challenging. For this reason, reliable PD indication is expected to rely on long-term monitoring of multiple BPL modem parameters rather than on instantaneous anomalies. In addition to throughput, parameters such as SNR, amplitude map, tone map, and BLE, as described in Section 5, provide complementary information about the state of the communication channel.

PD activity introduces impulsive disturbances that affect both the physical layer and the adaptive mechanisms of BPL modems. A decrease in throughput and effective link capacity is typically accompanied by an decrease in BLE and increase packet retransmissions, resulting in higher packet loss. At the frequency level, PD lead to localized degradation of SNR on affected sub-carriers, which may be excluded from transmission or assigned lower-order modulation schemes. Consequently, the tone map directly reflects these changes by adapting the number of transmitted bits per subcarrier, while the amplitude map captures variations in signal attenuation caused by discharge-induced disturbances.

Although a full time-domain evaluation of all BPL parameters is beyond the scope of this study, the presented results indicate that the combined analysis of throughput, BLE, SNR, and frequency-dependent modulation characteristics offers significant diagnostic potential. Correlating long-term trends of these parameters can improve the robustness of partial discharge detection in real network environments.

It was found that a total of 75% of failures in distribution networks are within the joints, terminations, and connections. This was also the conclusion of the CIRED Working Group WG 2021-3, who presented their report on the topic “Distribution Grid Underground Cables and Overhead Line Life Cycle” [53]. Of the total number of failures, it was also found that 65% were caused by poor assembly, failure to comply with all installation conditions, or poor heating, which results in an imperfect joint into which moisture can enter or be a cell that will generate PD. This corresponds precisely to Figure 6, where it is evident that the fusible green section did not adhere to the cable, indicating insufficient heating during installation. Figure 7 shows a degraded cable with a water tree that led to insulation breakdown.

If this PD detection method were to become one of the alternative options for evaluating the service life of cable assemblies, it would be necessary to consider the assembly of the coupling elements themselves. In the case of capacitive coupling elements, the assembly process is much more demanding than in the case of

FIGURE 6 | Inspection of the cable termination. The fusible material was not sufficiently heated along the entire length of the cable termination, resulting in a solid connection.

FIGURE 7 | In this figure you can see that the joint was heated better and the melt flowed better, but it was still not done correctly. This resulted in a breakthrough. The water tree is very clearly visible where it passed.

an inductive coupling element. In the case of using a capacitive coupling element, the PLC signal is injected primarily into the cable core, not into the entire cable, including the shield. This can have a significant impact on PD detection, but also on the potential robustness of the communication.

The method of measuring and obtaining data directly from the PLC modem depends on the possible access to the modem. Some PLC modem manufacturers allow the user to connect under administrator access, while others allow only user access. This can significantly limit the measurement and the obtaining of data for further secondary use. Even in cases where administrator access to the BPL modems is not available during measurement, several relevant parameters can still be obtained using alternative tools and methods (e.g., EXFO [additional measurement device], iPerf [SW tool]), as demonstrated in other studies [54–56]. If administrator access to the BPL modem is available, it is recommended to monitor a broader range of communication parameters. These extended measurements can significantly improve the accuracy of PD detection. Among them, the SNR profile is particularly valuable, as it reveals the specific frequency ranges affected by significant disturbances, which often correspond to PD activity.

The primary purpose of BPL technology lies in utilizing existing infrastructure—specifically, power cables in distribution networks—for communication between DTS. The DTS is typically connected to a SCADA system to enable dispatcher-level control, automation, and the monitoring of voltage, current, and other key electrical parameters within the DTS.

A secondary advantage of BPL is its potential to support PD detection and cable diagnostics, and to use the full diagnostic potential of the technology.

Although the use of BPL as a dedicated diagnostic tool for PD detection appears technically feasible, it may be economically challenging. A direct comparison of detection accuracy with purpose-built PD detection equipment was beyond the scope of this paper, but represents a valuable avenue for future research.

From a practical implementation perspective, the proposed approach is intended as a secondary use of existing BPL infrastructure rather than as a standalone partial discharge monitoring system. The underlying assumption is that BPL modems are already deployed by the utility provider for communication purposes, in which case PD indication can be obtained without additional sensing hardware and with minimal incremental cost. Deploying BPL technology solely for partial discharge detection would not be cost-effective compared to conventional diagnostic solutions.

Installation-related aspects, such as mechanical constraints of inductive or capacitive coupling elements and accessibility of medium-voltage cables in substations or cable compartments, can further influence feasibility. Nevertheless, the integration of BPL-based diagnostic indicators into existing SCADA systems represents a promising direction, as it enables centralized evaluation of communication and diagnostic data within a unified operational framework.

8 | Conclusion

This article explored the potential of secondary use of PLC/BPL technology as a diagnostic tool for detecting PD in MV cable lines. Given that PD is a key early indicator of insulation system degradation, its timely detection is critical for enabling predictive maintenance and ensuring the operational reliability of distribution networks. Ultimately, this approach can contribute to reducing SAIDI and SAIFI reliability indices.

Experimental results confirmed that certain BPL throughput respond sensitively and measurably to the occurrence of PD. Laboratory experiments on a real MV cable confirmed that these deviations can be captured using both inductive and capacitive couplers. Each coupling method offers distinct sensitivity and spectral response characteristics, suggesting that their combination could provide complementary insights.

The findings suggest that PLC/BPL systems can act as auxiliary sensors for real-time monitoring of cable health without requiring dedicated measurement equipment. This represents an efficient and cost-effective diagnostic solution, particularly for extensive distribution networks where traditional testing methods may be impractical.

Future research will focus on analyzing additional communication parameters offered by BPL modems that were not explored in this study (i.e., SNR, tonemap, link capacity, BLE). Several of these may hold high diagnostic value, either for identifying PD activity or for characterizing the transmission channel's overall condition.

Further work will also examine various discharge injection configurations. For instance, PD generation exclusively between the cable core-to-core and the shield-to-shield may correspond to specific fault scenarios in distribution networks (e.g., termination degradation, internal transformer faults inducing feedback into the core, or elevated shield-to-core voltages caused by poor grounding). Such scenarios may reveal whether different types or directions of PD activity can be distinguished based on changes in communication parameters.

Additionally, combined measurement approaches using mixed coupling techniques—such as one BPL modem connected via inductive coupling and another via capacitive coupling—will be evaluated. This hybrid setup could enhance the spectral coverage and diagnostic resolution, contributing to the development of a more robust and scalable use of BPL technology as an active diagnostic tool for power networks under real operating conditions.

From the perspective of distribution system operators, the proposed approach offers a practical means of enhancing network observability using existing communication infrastructure. By continuously monitoring selected BPL communication parameters, utilities can identify abnormal trends indicative of insulation degradation and prioritize targeted inspections or maintenance activities. Rather than replacing established diagnostic methods, the presented approach complements them by providing early warning indicators that can reduce the likelihood of unexpected cable failures and associated outage durations.

In practical deployment, BPL-based partial discharge indication can be integrated into existing operational workflows through centralized data acquisition and evaluation. Communication parameters collected by BPL modems can be periodically transmitted to supervisory systems, such as SCADA platforms, where long-term trends can be analyzed alongside conventional operational data. This enables condition-based maintenance strategies without requiring additional on-site measurements or dedicated PD monitoring equipment.

Author Contributions

Lukas Benesl: conceptualization, data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, resources, visualization, writing – original draft. **Petr Mlynek:** conceptualization, formal analysis, funding acquisition, investigation, project administration, supervision, validation, writing – original draft, writing – review & editing. **Michal Krbal:** formal analysis, funding acquisition, investigation, validation, writing – review & editing. **Martin Rusz:** formal analysis, resources, software. **Petr Musil:** data curation, methodology, resources. **Jiri Misurec:** formal analysis, supervision. **Jan Slacik:** formal analysis, resources, visualization.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no potential conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15806637>.

Endnotes

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